

The connection of the production and the energy usage in a smart factory

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Abstract. According to the newest industrial trends, the static and highly centralized networks are replaced by elastic, distributed, many autonomous, but linked components. By decentralizing industrial management, the goal is to achieve a more efficient resource utilization in the factories. The previous wasteful energy consumption cannot be maintained anymore. The process would impose a limit on production, which cannot be tolerated by the producers. The producing machines have built-in sensors, which are able to detect the disruption of energy input and its usage rate, and they can assign it with the resulting pieces, so the system can deduct the most efficient settings of the operating machines.

At a manufacturing company, the managers aim to develop their processes, which connect to the production. The development is not only a new method, but a new mentality, with which we are able to identify the problem area and solve it. The main problem was identified earlier, that is related to the wasteful energy use of manufacturer machines. Therefore, a data collector prototype system was implemented by us at the company.

This study demonstrates the challenges and their solutions from the viewpoint of timeline. In the last months, the prototype system was created for data collecting. These historical and real-time datasets are the basis of the analysis: first, we have cleaned and prepared the dataset, then the analysis of data is continually executed. This analysis helps us in getting the information. With forecasting methods, we can make estimates for the future events. The managers can get the daily reports about the production numbers and the energy use. In addition, we can focus the occurrences of critical events with defining the limit for risky parameters. The goal is to prevent the stoppage of the production or the excessive use of the energy. After we get the results of analysis, we will make decisions.

First, we have focused on the data collecting process. The company's supervisory system gives us the energy usage data of the selected manufacturing machines. We have chosen different machines, from the aspect of utilization of the energy (high, moderate, standard and low). The measurements are done by the data-collector sensors. We have built the communication network between the machines, sensors and the data-centers. In this way, we can keep under control the complete process in real-time. The energy usage of the machines would be constant, but there is no consideration of the various manufacturing at the company. We notice, that they produce circa 1500 different types of products. In addition, there is an upper limit of the energy usage a day, on average, that the company should comply

with it. So then, we must collect and select the data, which are connected to the production process. For example, produced products' type and quantity or shift data. At the end of this process, we merged the total sum of the fact data (that mentioned above) through the dimension data (time and machine identifiers). The merging progress is happened every 10 minutes. This time parameter can be modified by us at any time. Then, with help of a business intelligence software, we can analyze the time series of the various data. The managers can make decisions now easier than ever. However, we still have challenges with this system, for example, the reaching the fact data faster or the optimization of the analysis methods.

Our general goal is to make the manufacturing more efficient. In our presentation, we will demonstrate a decision support system at an international furniture company.

Keywords: manufacturing, energy management system, integrated solution.